

Screening tools for obstructive sleep apnea with applicability in pharmacy practice

Ivo Kumanov¹, Magdalena Pesheva¹, Velichka Andonova², Mario Milkov³, Galina Petrova¹

1 Department of Organisation and Economics in Pharmacy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Varna, Varna, Bulgaria

2 Department of Pharmaceutical Technologies, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Varna, Varna, Bulgaria

3 Department of Dental Material Science and Propaedeutics of Prosthetic Dental Medicine, Faculty of Dental medicine, Medical University of Varna, Varna, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Galina Petrova (galina.petrova@mu-varna.bg)

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Abstract

Obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) as the most common sleep disorder, is associated with increased morbidity and mortality from cardiovascular diseases and traffic injuries. Sleep disorders, particularly those resulting from sleep apnea, despite their significant health and financial burden, are poorly recognized, often underdiagnosed, and ineffectively managed. Screening, diagnosing, and adequately treating OSA requires multidisciplinary teamwork and an individualized approach to patients with sleep disorders. Pharmacists, as some of the most accessible health professionals integrated into interdisciplinary teams, can provide complementary clinical (pharmacy) services for screening, health education, monitoring, and management of sleep disorders and OSA.

Keywords

sleep disorders, questionnaire, risk, benefits, costs

Introduction

Sleep disorders are associated with significant health costs to society worldwide. Poor sleep quality is a risk factor for the development of cardiovascular, neurological and endocrine diseases as well as mental disorders and cancer (Blenkinsopp et al. 2003).

OSA is a common sleep-related breathing disorder in adults and children. It is characterised by brief and recurrent interruptions in breathing due to obstructive events in the upper airway during sleep (Dopp et al. 2007). These recurrent interruptions may be complete, apnea and/or partial, hypopnoea, resulting in intermittent hypoxaemia, autonomic fluctuations and sleep fragmentation (Yeghiazarians et al. 2021). The apnea-hypopnoea index (AHI) is widely used

to determine the severity of OSA (Malhotra and White 2002). The AHI quantifies episodes of apnea and hypopnea. Depending on the number of apneas and hypopneas per hour, OSA can be classified as mild (AHI ≥ 5 to < 15 events/hour), moderate (AHI ≥ 15 to < 30 events/hour), or severe (AHI ≥ 30 events/hour) (Martinez et al. 2012). Statistically, there are 936 million people with mild to severe OSA and 425 million people with moderate to severe OSA aged between 30 and 69 years worldwide (Benjafield et al. 2019). The countries with the highest prevalence of OSA are China, USA, Brazil and India (Jaiswal et al. 2017; Benjafield et al. 2019).

According to epidemiological studies, the disease affects both men about 3–7% of all men and women approx 2–5% of all women (Netzer et al. 1999; Dimitrova and Genov 2015; Turner et al. 2021). The incidence of OSA may exceed 50%

in some conditions such as arterial hypertension, cardiac arrhythmia, and diabetes mellitus (Yuksel et al. 2010).

The disorder is correlated with high morbidity and mortality due to the risk of cardiovascular disease and traffic injuries (Gauld et al. 2019).

When OSA is untreated, in addition to the direct medical costs associated with the disease and other comorbidities (Smith et al. 2002; Senaratna et al. 2017), there are also indirect costs associated with impaired vigilance (i.e. motor vehicle crashes, occupational accidents, lost productivity, and absenteeism) (Tregear et al. 2010; Santschi et al. 2011).

In 2015, the cost of diagnosing and treating OSA in the United States was approximately \$12.4 billion (Turner et al. 2021). Approximately 30–40% of adult patients at high risk for developing sleep apnea do not report symptoms, and less than one-third of patients at high risk for OSA have sleep-related symptoms documented in their medical records (Marti-Soler et al. 2016; Mold et al. 2011). The annual cost of treatment and medical care for sleep disorders is approximately \$94.9 billion (Hersberger et al. 2006).

In Australia the prevalence of OSA ranges from 9% to 38% of the population, contributing to an estimated annual cost of \$66 billion attributed to sleep disorders (Saleh et al. 2011). Among the adult population in Bulgaria, OSA affects approximately 5% to 10% (Yancheva et al. 2021). Despite the considerable health and financial impact of these conditions, sleep disorders - particularly those caused by OSA - remain underrecognized, underdiagnosed, and inadequately managed (Reis et al. 2014; Benjafield et al. 2019).

The care of patients with OSA varies between countries and depends on the symptoms of the patient (Huyett and Bhattacharyya 2021). Screening and management of OSA remains a problem. Challenges in the management of OSA are related to underdiagnosis and complex, fragmented patient care (Basheti et al. 2021). Sleep medicine as a multidisciplinary field has only existed for four decades. It requires special training, interdisciplinary teamwork and an individualised approach to patients with sleep disorders (Yancheva et al. 2021).

The high prevalence of OSA poses a serious economic burden to society (Smith et al. 2002), necessitating the development of new approaches to diagnosis and timely treatment (Watson 2016). One such approach is pharmacist-led screening to detect early signs of disease development in order to refer the patient to the appropriate specialist.

In a number of countries such as the USA, Canada, Australia, and some of the EU, the role of the community pharmacist who traditionally dispenses prescriptions has changed significantly in the last few years (Anderson 2000). Integrated into multidisciplinary teams, pharmacists can provide additional clinical (pharmacy) services such as screening, health education, monitoring, and chronic disease management collaboration with other health care providers (e.g., GPs, nurses, and other medical professionals), including for sleep disorders and OSA inclusive (Giles et al. 2006; Yuksel et al. 2010; Santschi et al. 2011; Perraudin et al. 2013; Gauld et al. 2019; Turner et al. 2021).

The aim of this study is to present possible validated tools for pharmacist screening for the detection of early signs of obstructive sleep apnea.

Material and methods

A content analysis of the literature related to sleep disorders and the role of pharmacists in the implementation of screening for obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) was used for this study. A literature search was conducted in PubMed as well as other established scientific databases using the following keywords: ‚sleep apnea‘, ‚sleep disorders‘, OSA screening‘ and ‚validated OSA questionnaires‘.

Research articles that met the following criteria were included in the study: presence of at least one of these keywords in the title, abstract, or main text of the publication; published in full text in the time period considered (1999–2024); studies involving individuals over 18 years of age; and relevance to the topic - publications must address sleep disorders and/or the role of pharmacists in OSA screening programs.

Articles that met one or more the following criteria were excluded: no full-text version of the publication; studies involving individuals under 18 years of age; irrelevance to the topic at hand - for example, studies focused on OSA treatment with no link to screening activities conducted by pharmacists.

A total of 1025 scientific publications were identified in the initial search. After application of the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the number of articles analysed was reduced as follows: 545 publications were excluded due to lack of full text; 245 publications were excluded because they included individuals under 18 years of age; 202 publications were rejected due to lack of direct relevance to the topic.

Forty-nine scientific publications were included in the detailed analysis – 33 articles from PubMed and 16 publications from other scientific databases. The articles analyzed covered various aspects of the topic, including validated OSA questionnaires, screening programs developed, and pharmacists‘ involvement in identifying patients at risk for OSA (Fig. 1).

Results and discussion

OSA is an important disease characterised by recurrent pauses in breathing during sleep due to upper airway collapse (Malhotra and White 2002).

Given the prevalence of OSA and its physiological consequences in some patients, making a correct diagnosis with a polysomnographic test (PSG) is of great clinical importance. In OSA, recurrent respiratory arrest (apnea) or partial upper airway obstruction (hypopnoea) is observed during sleep. The disease has various manifestations such as snoring, severe daytime sleepiness, nervousness, lack of concentration, depression, lack of sexual desire, hypertension and insulin resistance (Young et al. 2002). Many factors increase the risk of developing OSA (Fig. 2) (Young et al. 2002; Pivetta et al. 2021).

The changing role of the pharmacist over the past three decades is a result of the evolution of the concept of pharmaceutical care as „the responsible provision of drug therapy to achieve specific outcomes with the goal of improving the quality of life of patients“ (Kapur et al. 2017).

Figure 1. PRISMA flowchart about the the publication selection process.

Figure 2. Risk factors for the occurrence of OSA.

The expanded role of the community pharmacist in providing pharmaceutical services includes screening; health education; therapeutic education; prevention services, and chronic disease management, with a proven positive impact on health outcomes. This has led to the development of alternative strategies for screening programs in primary care that include the pharmacist as a interdisciplinary team member (Perraudin et al. 2013). In the pharmacy, the community pharmacist can identify risk OSA factors, which can help recognize persons at risk.

In this context, pharmacists can play a key role in the screening and early diagnosis of sleep apnea syndrome. Intervention trials involving pharmacists, particularly in screening and monitoring of cardiovascular disease, and diabetes, are not new and demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of services provided by pharmacists (Blenkinsopp et al. 2003; Koshman et al. 2008; Vakrilova-Becheva et al. 2023; Peneva et al. 2024).

The growing role of pharmacists in primary care in keeping pace with current trends in pharmaceutical care

suggests their involvement in various screening programs, including to detect early signs of OSA (Fig. 3).

Perraudin et al. (2013) examined the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of a pharmacist-led community-based OSA screening program. Based on a cost-benefit analysis, the results show that a pharmacist-led screening strategy is more effective and less costly than traditional screening methods. In the study, the authors used the Markov model to assess different health conditions and the probabilities of transition between them, allowing for a better understanding of the long-term effects of continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) treatment. The researchers have highlighted the importance of expanding the role of pharmacists in primary care, particularly in the context of health care reforms being implemented in a number of countries, including France, the USA and the Great Britain. These reforms allow for greater involvement of pharmacists in the delivery of primary care services and in the therapeutic education of patients. It also implies improved access to healthcare and better health outcomes for patients (Perraudin et al. 2013).

Questionnaire name	Assessment	Threshold value	Advantages	Disadvantages
STOP-Bang	0 to 8 points	3 points	Useful as a screening tool to detect OSA. The higher the score, the greater the likelihood of severe OSA	Composed of subjective and objective answers
NoSAS	from 0 to 17 points	7 points	Easy to use because it consists of only 5 elements. Almost all items can be easily measured and are objective. Can be administered to demanding populations (e.g., severe depression).	-
Berlin Questionnaire	High risk: if there are 2 or more categories where the result is positive. Low risk: if there is only 1 or no category in which the result is positive.	-	-	Almost all answers questions can be subjective

Figure 3. Questionnaires were used to assess the likelihood and severity of OSA before the polysomnographic test. Source: (Małolepsza et al. 2021).

In the international context of the field of sleep, research on the role of pharmacists has focused primarily on screening, reviewing inappropriate use of medication products (MP), and monitoring the treatment of patients with sleep problems (Perraudin et al. 2013; Gauld et al. 2019; Turner et al. 2021).

Screening programmes to detect sleep disorders have been conducted in Switzerland, and several studies have shown the results of implemented programmes (Hersberger et al. 2006).

Several studies conducted in Australia have also highlighted the benefits of community pharmacist care, particularly in the management of insomnia and screening for OSA (Blenkinsopp, Anderson, and Armstrong 2003). Pharmacists in Australia play a significant role in the provision of OSA identification services (Hanes et al. 2015).

The researchers concluded that pharmacists can help identify patients at risk of OSA by participating in a targeted population screening program. Screening for OSA by a pharmacist most often involves gathering information about the patient's symptoms, risk factors and patient's health status. The pharmacist can use various tools and questionnaires to identify potential cases of OSA and refer patients for further investigation.

Early diagnosis and timely treatment of sleep disorders would reduce the economic impact on health systems and the community. For this reason, the community pharmacy is an appropriate location for screening and early intervention compared to other primary care settings due to its greater accessibility (Hersberger et al. 2006).

Although PSG examination is the gold standard for diagnosing OSA, its application by pharmacists is limited by various factors related to workload, cost and educational background. According to Ramasamy (2018), community pharmacists are ideally equipped to use clinically validated tools to identify patients who may be at risk for OSA

(Chidambaram 2018). There are a number of questionnaires in the scientific literature that are suitable for assessing the likelihood and severity of OSA prior to PSG testing. These questionnaires are easy-to-administer and inexpensive tools that have been used by various researchers around the world. They have different sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV) and negative predictive value (NPV) in different populations (Małolepsza et al. 2021).

The study set criteria for the selection of questionnaires based on publications with results from validated tools to determine the risk of developing obstructive sleep apnea among adult patients, with the possibility of application by pharmacists. These related to the specific work of pharmacists and their ability to participate in various screening programmes, including OSA screening. For validated tests, the criteria for application by pharmacists are as follows: time to complete the instrument, accuracy and ability to quickly calculate the results obtained. From the analysis performed, we selected three questionnaires that met the set criteria and were suitable for implementation by pharmacists. The questionnaires are summarized in Fig. 3, which presents the 3 validated instruments and the advantages and disadvantages of each of them.

STOP-BANG questionnaire

The STOP questionnaire was developed in response to the need for a user-friendly, quick and short questionnaire to screen patients for OSA before surgery in surgical clinics (Chung et al. 2008; Chung et al. 2012). It consists of four yes/no questions about snoring, fatigue, observed apnea, and hypertension (STOP). The STOP-BANG was developed to further improve the sensitivity of the STOP questionnaire and to detect patients with moderate and severe OSA (Chung et al. 2008). It consists of 8 items related to subjective perceptions and clinical characteristics (Luong

et al. 2024). The abbreviation BANG is derived from the first letters of the characteristics: Body mass index (BMI), Age, Neck circumference (neck circumference ≥ 43 in men, ≥ 41 in women) and Gender, which are assessed at the time of questionnaire administration. These characteristics are also described by yes/no answers, making the scale quick and easy to complete. A yes answer for each question is worth 1 point and a no answer is worth 0. A score of 1 is given for age > 50 years, neck circumference ≥ 43 cm for men and ≥ 41 cm for women, and BMI > 35 kg/m². The total score ranged from 0 to 8 (Fig. 4).

Amra et al. (2018) investigated the value of screening questionnaires for the diagnosis of OSA, and their validity compared to PSG as the gold standard. Studies have shown that the STOP and STOP-BANG questionnaires are practical tools for identifying patients at high risk of OSA, which is essential for timely treatment and prevention of associated health risks. The authors emphasize the need for accurate evaluation of screening tools to improve diagnosis and management of the condition, especially in diverse populations (Amra et al. 2018).

A study on the prevalence of OSA in Cyprus, conducted in 2019 using a modified STOP-BANG questionnaire among 4118 respondents, found that 50% of men and 18% of women in the general population were at intermediate to high risk for OSA. The results suggest that OSA is a common condition, particularly among middle-aged and obese men, and highlight the need for further research in southern Europe, where data on OSA prevalence is limited. The authors of the Frangopoulos et al. study emphasise that OSA is a serious health problem with a high prevalence in Cyprus, especially among men and obese individuals. They stress the importance of using reliable screening tool, such as the STOP-BANG questionnaire to identify at-risk groups. They argue that screening tools

cannot replace clinical diagnosis and stress the need for further research in Southern Europe to better understand the factors contributing to the prevalence of this condition (Frangopoulos et al. 2019).

Another investigation by Labarca et al. (2019) found high susceptibility to obstructive sleep apnea-hypopnoea syndrome (OSAHS) in hospitalised patients, with 34.92% at risk of major cardiovascular events. Results from the STOP-BANG questionnaire showed a significant association between elevated scores and cardiovascular events, particularly in patients aged 40–79 years. Furthermore, a history of heart failure independently predicted major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE). The authors highlighted the need for early identification of at-risk patients using the cost-effective STOP-BANG tool and advocated the integration of OSAHS screening into existing cardiovascular risk models to improve patient management and reduce morbidity and mortality. Limitations, such as limited access to diagnostic tests, were noted, but the results of the study emphasize the need to integrate OSAHS risk assessment into broader health strategies (Labarca et al. 2019).

In 2021, Pivetta et al. (2021) confirmed the opinion of other researchers that the STOP-BANG questionnaire, with its high sensitivity and diagnostic accuracy, is a valuable tool for screening OSA. The review includes data from several studies evaluating the sensitivity and specificity of the tool and highlights the importance of demographic characteristics of the population in the prevalence of OSA. They suggest that the questionnaire may help to identify patients with OSA at an early stage, which is essential for the prevent on as health risks. The authors emphasise the need to adapt the tool to the specific characteristics of different populations in order to ensure optimal screening performance (Pivetta et al. 2021).

S	Snoring?	Do you snore loudly (loud enough to be heard through closed doors or to have your bed partner elbow you because you snore at night)?	Yes No
T	Tired?	Do you often feel tired, sleepy or drowsy during the day (for example, falling asleep while driving or talking to someone)?	Yes No
O	Observed?	Has anyone ever seen you stop breathing or choke/gasp during sleep?	Yes No
P	Pressure?	Do you have high blood pressure or are you being treated for it?	Yes No
B	BMI	Body mass index over 35 kg/m ² ?	Yes No
A	Age	Age over 50?	Yes No
N	Neck size	Neck size / shirt collar 16 inches / 40cm or larger? (measured around Adam's apple)	Yes No
G	Gender	Sex = Male?	Yes No

Figure 4. STOP-BANG questionnaire. Source: (Małolepsza et al. 2021).

Evidence from several studies suggests that the higher the STOP-BANG score, the greater the likelihood of severe OSA (up to 95% for a score of 6). In contrast, a score of less than 3 indicates high discriminatory power for excluding moderate or severe OSA (Punjabi 2008; Farney et al. 2011; Amra et al. 2018; Kuczyński et al. 2019).

NoSAS Questionnaire

NoSAS has been developed as a new screening tool to identify patients at risk of sleep-disordered breathing (Hanes et al. 2015). The NoSAS score consists of five items and a specific number of points for each item (Fig. 5). Neck circumference > 40 cm was given 4 points, body mass index (BMI) between 25 and < 30 kg/m² 3 points, BMI ≥ 30 kg/m² 5 points, age > 55 years 4 points and male sex 2 points. The total number of points ranged from 0 to 17 (Coutinho Costa et al. 2019; Luong et al. 2024).

A study by Coutinho Costa (Coutinho Costa et al. 2019) in patients referred to a sleep unit by primary care physicians showed that sensitivity and PPV were 94.3% and 87.6%, respectively, for all OSA severity categories, using a cut-off value of 7 points. At the same cut-off, the NPV for all OSA grades was 50%. In another study conducted in a group of patients with suspected sleep-disordered breathing, NoSAS showed 71.6% sensitivity, 68.7% specificity, 89.0% PPV and 40.7% NPV for the detection of OSA (Duarte et al. 2018).

According to Guichard et al. (2018), the main advantage of the NoSAS questionnaire is that it contains a small number of items that can be measured quickly and objectively. Its ease of use allows it to be applied to challenging populations, such as patients with major depression (Guichard et al. 2018).

Berlin Questionnaire (BQ)

The Berlin Questionnaire to identify patients in primary care at risk of OSA was developed in 1999 (Netzer et al. 1999). The questionnaire is divided into three categories

(Fig. 6): the first concerns snoring; the second sleepiness and fatigue; and the last the presence of hypertension. High risk in category 1 is defined as persistent symptoms with two or more questions concerning the presence of snoring. High risk in category 2 is defined as persistent drowsiness on waking, drowsiness on driving, or the presence of both. High blood pressure in category 3 is the indicator of high risk. Patients at high risk in at least two categories are considered to be at increased risk of OSA (Sake et al. 2019).

A study by Saleh et al. (2011) showed that the sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV using BQ were 97%, 90%, 96% and 93%, respectively, for AHI > 5 events/hour (Saleh et al. 2011). Similar sensitivity for predicting OSA was found by El-Sayed (2012) at 95%, but he reported a specificity of only 23%, and PPV and NPV of 92% and 33%, respectively (El-Sayed 2012). The researcher estimated these parameters with cut-off values of AHI > 15 events/hour and AHI > 30 events/hour. These results indicate that the Berlin questionnaire has high sensitivity for detecting moderate to severe (95%) and severe OSA (97%), but very low specificity for detecting moderate to mild (7%) and mild OSA (10%) (El-Sayed 2012).

Overview

As a result of our review of the literature on OSA and questionnaires to assess the likelihood and severity of OSA, we believe that these questionnaires can be used by pharmacists in pharmacy practice, in addition to sleep specialists, to screen for OSA. The STOP-BANG and NoSAS tests are applicable in the Bulgarian setting. In order to identify patients at risk of OSA, we suggest adding additional questions should be added to the questionnaire about sleep disturbance, use of OTC insomnia medication, presence of diabetes and lung disease. If pharmacists identify patients with suspected OSA, they will be referred to a sleep specialist for polysomnographic examination, diagnosis and subsequent treatment.

Figure 5. NoSAS Questionnaire. Source: (Marti-Soler et al. 2016).

Height (m) -----	Weight (kg) -----	Age -----	Male/ female		
Please choose the correct response to each question.					
Category 1					
Do you snore?	Yes	No	Don't know		
Your snoring is	A little louder than your breath	As loud as you can talk	Louder than talking	Very loud - can be heard in adjacent rooms	
How often do you snore?	Almost every day	3-4 times weekly	1-2 times weekly	1-2 times monthly	Never, or almost never, ever
Has your snoring ever disturbed other people?	Yes	No	Don't know		
Has anyone noticed that your breathing stops when you are asleep?	Almost every day	3-4 times weekly	1-2 times weekly	1-2 times monthly	Never, or almost never, ever
Category 2					
How often do you feel tired or worn out after you sleep?	Almost every day	3-4 times weekly	1-2 times weekly	1-2 times monthly	Never, or almost never, ever
Are you tired, exhausted or feeling under the weather when you wake up?	Almost every day	3-4 times weekly	1-2 times weekly	1-2 times monthly	Never, or almost never, ever
Have you ever fallen asleep at the wheel of a car or had a nap?	Yes	No			
If yes	Almost every day	3-4 times weekly	1-2 times weekly	1-2 times monthly	Never, or almost never, ever
How often does this occur?					
Category 3					
Do you have high blood pressure?	Yes	No	Don't know		

Figure 6. Berlin Questionnaire. Source: (Netzer et al. 1999).

By using each of the listed questionnaires as a tool, pharmacists can effectively identify patients at risk. Early detection of OSA will help increase the number of diagnosed cases of a condition that often goes undiagnosed and untreated, and will reduce the risk of serious complications such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes, depression, etc. The benefits to the healthcare system will be reduced treatment costs, increased public awareness, improved adherence to treatment and improved quality of life for patients.

Conclusion

The experience of pharmacists in providing pharmaceutical care for chronic diseases such as diabetes, CVD, asthma, etc. would be useful for implementing OSA screening in the community pharmacy during patient visits for dispensing and monitoring of existing diseases. A number of studies have shown that the implementation of screening programs to determine the risk of sleep apnea development by pharmacists is cost-effective for the patient him/herself and cost-effective for the health care system and society as a whole.

Trends in pharmaceutical care indicate an expanding role for pharmacists and their more active involvement in primary care. The validated OSA screening tools STOP-Bang, NoSAS and Berlin Questionnaire are suitable for implementation by pharmacists because of their ability to conduct screening quickly, process easily and obtain clear results.

Development of a standardized framework (model) for the provision of pharmaceutical care in sleep apnea would improve health outcomes and reduce overall healthcare costs, and collaboration between pharmacists and other healthcare professionals would help improve OSA management and patients' quality of life.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Ivo Kumanov <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7272-5356>

Magdalena Pesheva <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2478-1177>

Velichka Andonova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7369-1506>

Mario Milkov <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0794-7355>

Galina Petrova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5826-2076>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Amra B, Rahmati B, Soltaninejad F, Feizi A (2018) Screening Questionnaires for Obstructive Sleep Apnea: An Updated Systematic Review. *Oman Medical Journal* 33(3): 184–192. <https://doi.org/10.5001/omj.2018.36>
- Anderson C (2000) Health Promotion in Community Pharmacy: The UK Situation. *Patient Education and Counseling* 39(2–3): 285–91. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0738-3991\(99\)00025-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0738-3991(99)00025-7)
- Basheti M, Gordon C, Bawa Z, Grunstein R, Saini B (2021) Sleep health management in community pharmacy: Where are we and where should we be heading? *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy* 17(11): 1945–1956. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sapharm.2021.02.011>
- Benjafield A, Ayas N, Eastwood P, Heinzer R, Ip M, Morrell M, Nunez C, Patel S, Penzel T, Pépin JL, Peppard P, Sinha S, Tufik S, Valentine K, Malhotra A (2019) Estimation of the global prevalence and burden of obstructive sleep apnoea: a literature-based analysis. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine* 7(8): 687–698. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600\(19\)30198-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600(19)30198-5)
- Blenkinsopp A, Anderson C, Armstrong M (2003) Systematic review of the effectiveness of community pharmacy-based interventions to reduce risk behaviours and risk factors for coronary heart disease. *Journal of Public Health Medicine* 25(2): 144–153. <https://doi.org/10.1093/pubmed/fdg030>
- Chidambaram R (2018) Good News: Family Medicine Specialists Have More Opportunity to Diagnose Undiagnosed Sleep Apnea in Children. *The Malaysian Journal of Medical Sciences* 25(5): 160–161. <https://doi.org/10.21315/mjms2018.25.5.16>
- Chung F, Subramanyam R, Liao P, Sasaki E, Shapiro C, Sun Y (2012) High STOP-Bang Score Indicates a High Probability of Obstructive Sleep Apnea. *British Journal of Anaesthesia* 108(5): 768–775. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bja/aes022>
- Chung F, Yegneswaran B, Liao P, Chung SA, Vairavanathan S, Islam S, Khajehdehi A, Shapiro CM (2008) STOP questionnaire: a tool to screen patients for obstructive sleep apnea. *Anesthesiology* 108(5): 812–821. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ALN.0b013e31816d83e4>
- Coutinho C, Rebelo-Marques A, Machado J, Gama J, Santos C, Teixeira F, Moita J (2019) Validation of NoSAS (Neck, Obesity, Snoring, Age, Sex) score as a screening tool for obstructive sleep apnea: Analysis in a sleep clinic. *Pulmonology* 25(5): 263–270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pulmoe.2019.04.004>
- Dimitrova M, Genov K (2015) Neurological Aspects of Obstructive Sleep Apnea. *Military Medicine* 3(4): 11–15.
- Dopp J, Reichmuth K, Morgan B (2007) Obstructive sleep apnea and hypertension: mechanisms, evaluation, and management. *Current Hypertension Reports* 9(6): 529–534. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11906-007-0095-2>
- Duarte R, Rabahi M, Magalhães-da-Silveira F, de Oliveira-E-Sá T, Melo F, Gozal D (2018) Simplifying the Screening of Obstructive Sleep Apnea With a 2-Item Model, No-Apnea: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine* 14(7): 1097–1107. <https://doi.org/10.5664/jcsm.7202>
- El-Sayed I (2012) Comparison of Four Sleep Questionnaires for Screening Obstructive Sleep Apnea. *Egyptian Journal of Chest Diseases and Tuberculosis* 61(4): 433–441. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejcdt.2012.07.003>
- Farney R, Walker B, Farney R, Snow G, Walker J (2011) The STOP-Bang equivalent model and prediction of severity of obstructive sleep apnea: relation to polysomnographic measurements of the apnea/hypopnea index. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine* 7(5): 459–65B. <https://doi.org/10.5664/JCSM.1306>
- Fatema-Tun-Naher S, Wong K, Bartlett D, Saini B (2019) Insomnia management in the Australian primary care setting. *Behavioral Sleep Medicine* 17(1): 19–30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15402002.2016.1266491>
- Frangopoulos F, Nicolaou I, Zannetos S, Economou NT, Adamide T, Georgiou A, Trakada G (2019) Estimating obstructive sleep apnea in Cyprus: a randomised, stratified epidemiological study using STOP-Bang sleep apnea questionnaire. *Sleep Medicine* 61: 37–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleep.2019.04.013>
- Gauld N, Braganza C, Arroll B (2019) Adapting the Auckland Sleep Screening Tool for pharmacy: pharmacists' experience and feedback. *Journal of Primary Health Care* 11(2): 170–177. <https://doi.org/10.1071/HC19003>
- Giles T, Lasserson T, Smith B, White J, Wright J, Cates C (2006) Continuous positive airways pressure for obstructive sleep apnoea in adults. *The Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* 25(1): CD001106. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD001106.pub2>
- Guichard K, Marti-Soler H, Micoulaud-Franchi JA, Philip P, Marques-Vidal P, Vollenweider P, Waeber G, Preisig M, Haba-Rubio J, Heinzer R (2018) The NoSAS score: A new and simple screening tool for obstructive sleep apnea syndrome in depressive disorder. *Journal of Affective Disorders* 227: 136–140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2017.10.015>
- Hanes C, Wong K, Saini B (2015) Consolidating innovative practice models: The case for obstructive sleep apnea services in Australian pharmacies. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy* 11(3): 412–427. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sapharm.2014.08.009>
- Hersberger K, Renggli V, Nirkko A, Mathis J, Schwegler K, Bloch K (2006) Screening for sleep disorders in community pharmacies--evaluation of a campaign in Switzerland. *Journal of Clinical Pharmacy and Therapeutics* 31(1): 35–41. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2710.2006.00698.x>
- Huyett P, Bhattacharyya N (2021) Incremental health care utilization and expenditures for sleep disorders in the United States. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine* 17(10): 1981–1986. <https://doi.org/10.5664/jcsm.9392>
- Jaiswal S, Owens R, Malhotra A (2017) Raising awareness about sleep disorders. *Lung India: Official Organ of Indian Chest Society* 34(3): 262–268. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0970-2113.205331>
- Kapur V, Auckley D, Chowdhuri S, Kuhlmann D, Mehra R, Ramar K, Harrod C (2017) Clinical Practice Guideline for Diagnostic Testing for Adult Obstructive Sleep Apnea: An American Academy of Sleep Medicine Clinical Practice Guideline. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine* 13(3): 479–504. <https://doi.org/10.5664/jcsm.6506>
- Koshman S, Charrois T, Simpson S, McAlister F, Tsuyuki R (2008) Pharmacist care of patients with heart failure: a systematic review of randomized trials. *Archives of Internal Medicine* 168(7): 687–694. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archinte.168.7.687>
- Kuczynski W, Mokros Ł, Stolarz A, Białasiewicz P (2019) The utility of STOP-BANG questionnaire in the sleep-lab setting. *Scientific Reports* 9(1): 6676. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-43199-2>
- Labarca G, Valdivia G, Oñate A, Navarrete C, Araya J, Fernandez-Bussy I, Dreyse J, Jorquera J (2019) Prevalence of STOP BANG questionnaire

- and association with major cardiovascular events in hospitalized population: is it enough with currently used cardiovascular risk measurements? *Sleep Medicine*, 61: 82–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleep.2019.02.019>
- Luong S, Lezama L, Khan S (2024) Diagnosis and management of obstructive sleep apnea: Updates and review. *Journal of Otorhinolaryngology, Hearing and Balance Medicine* 5(2): 16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ohbm5020016>
- Malhotra A, White D (2002) Obstructive sleep apnoea. *Lancet* 360 (9328): 237–245. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(02\)09464-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(02)09464-3)
- Małolepsza A, Kudrycka A, Karwowska U, Hoshino T, Wibowo E, Pál Bőjti P, Białas A, Kuczyński W (2021) The role of screening questionnaires in the assessment of risk and severity of obstructive sleep apnea - polysomnography versus polygraphy. *Advances in Respiratory Medicine* 89(2): 188–196. <https://doi.org/10.5603/ARM.a2021.0038>
- Martinez D, da Silva R, Klein C, Fiori C, Massierer D, Cassol C, Bos A, Gus M (2012) High risk for sleep apnea in the Berlin questionnaire and coronary artery disease. *Sleep Breath* 16(1): 89–94. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11325-010-0460-2>
- Marti-Soler H, Hirotsu C, Marques-Vidal P, Vollenweider P, Waeber G, Preisig M, Tafti M, Tufik SB, Bittencourt L, Tufik S, Haba-Rubio J, Heinzer R (2016) The NoSAS score for screening of sleep-disordered breathing: a derivation and validation study. *The Lancet. Respiratory Medicine* 4(9): 742–748. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600\(16\)30075-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600(16)30075-3)
- Mold J, Quattlebaum C, Schinnerer E, Boeckman L, Orr W, Hollabaugh K (2011) Identification by primary care clinicians of patients with obstructive sleep apnea: a practice-based research network (PBRN) study. *Journal of the American Board of Family Medicine* 24(2): 138–45. <https://doi.org/10.3122/jabfm.2011.02.100095>
- Netzer NC, Stoohs RA, Netzer CM, Clark K, Strohl KP (1999) Using the Berlin Questionnaire to identify patients at risk for the sleep apnea syndrome. *Annals of Internal Medicine* 131(7): 485–491. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-131-7-199910050-00002>
- Peneva A, Dimitrov M, Petkova V (2024) Comparative analysis of newer classes of antidiabetics and the concept of pharmaceutical care – dealing with therapeutic problems. *Pharmacia* 71: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.71.e120141>
- Perraudin C, Le Vaillant M, Pelletier-Fleury N (2013) Cost-effectiveness of a community pharmacist-led sleep apnea screening program - a markov model. *PLoS ONE* 8(6): e63894. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0063894>
- Pivetta B, Chen L, Nagappa M, Saripella A, Waseem R, Englesakis M, Chung F (2021) Use and performance of the stop-bang questionnaire for obstructive sleep apnea screening across geographic regions: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *JAMA Network* 4(3): e211009. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2021.1009>
- Punjabi N (2008) The epidemiology of adult obstructive sleep apnea. *Proceedings of the American Thoracic Society* 5(2): 136–143. <https://doi.org/10.1513/pats.200709-155MG>
- Reis R, Teixeira F, Martins V, Sousa L, Batata L, Santos C, Moutinho J (2015) Validation of a Portuguese version of the STOP-Bang questionnaire as a screening tool for obstructive sleep apnea: Analysis in a sleep clinic. *Revista Portuguesa de Pneumologia* 21(2): 61–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rppneu.2014.04.007>
- Saleh A, Ahmad M, Awadalla N (2011) Development of Arabic version of Berlin questionnaire to identify obstructive sleep apnea at risk patients. *Annals of Thoracic Medicine* 6(4): 212–216. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1817-1737.84775>
- Santschi V, Chiolero A, Burnand B, Colosimo A, Paradis G (2011) Impact of pharmacist care in the management of cardiovascular disease risk factors: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized trials. *Archives of Internal Medicine* 171(16): 1441–1453. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archinternmed.2011.399>
- Senaratna C, Perret J, Lodge C, Lowe A, Campbell B, Matheson M, Hamilton G, Dharmage S (2017) Prevalence of obstructive sleep apnea in the general population: A systematic review. *Sleep Medicine Reviews* 34 (August): 70–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smrv.2016.07.002>
- Smith R, Ronald J, Delaive K, Walld R, Manfreda J, Kryger MH (2002) What are obstructive sleep apnea patients being treated for prior to this diagnosis? *Chest Journal* 121(1): 164–172. <https://doi.org/10.1378/chest.121.1.164>
- Tregear S, Reston J, Schoelles K, Phillips B (2010) Continuous positive airway pressure reduces risk of motor vehicle crash among drivers with obstructive sleep apnea: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Sleep* 33(10): 1373–1380. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/33.10.1373>
- Turner J, Sanyal C, Martin P, Tannenbaum C (2021) Economic evaluation of sedative deprescribing in older adults by community pharmacists. *The Journals of Gerontology. Series A, Biological Sciences and Medical Sciences* 76(6): 1061–1067. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gerona/glaa180>
- Vakriloova-Becheva M, Kirkova-Bogdanova A, Ivanova S, Atanasov P, Chaneva M, Petkova V (2023) Prevention of cardiovascular diseases. *Pharmacia* 70(4): 1243–1247. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.70.e114071>
- Watson N (2016) Health care savings: The economic value of diagnostic and therapeutic care for obstructive sleep apnea. *Journal of clinical sleep medicine. JCSM: Official Publication of the American Academy of Sleep Medicine* 12(8): 1075–1077. <https://doi.org/10.5664/jcsm.6034>
- Yancheva S, Dimitrova M, Tsvetkova V (2021) Obstructive sleep apnea, medico-social dimensions, nursing approaches in prevention and diagnosis. *Varna Medical Forum* 10(2): 438–442. <https://doi.org/10.14748/vmf.v10i2.7949>
- Yeghiazarians Y, Jneid H, Tietjens J, Redline S, Brown D, El-Sherif N, Mehra R, Bozkurt B, Ndumele C, Somers V (2022) Obstructive sleep apnea and cardiovascular disease: A scientific statement from the American heart association. *Circulation* 144(3): e56–e67. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIR.0000000000000988>
- Young T, Peppard P, Gottlieb D (2002) Epidemiology of obstructive sleep apnea: a population health perspective. *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine* 165(9): 1217–1239. <https://doi.org/10.1164/rccm.2109080>
- Yuksel N, Majumdar S, Biggs C, Tsuyuki R (2010) Community pharmacist-initiated screening program for osteoporosis: randomized controlled trial. *Osteoporosis International* 21(3): 391–398. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00198-009-0977-z>